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INNOVATIVE AND INCORPORATING WAYS TO IMPROVE THE EFFICIENCY OF PRESCHOOL EDUCATION

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Annotation. This article analyses the different ways to implement in the preschool education in order to enhance its efficacy. The authors have discussed and analyzed the possible methods to implement, together with providing relevant examples and merits and demerits.

Key words: preschool education, play based learning, nature-based learning, technology-based learning, mindfulness-based learning, multi-sensory learning, collaborative learning.

Preschool education plays a vital role in shaping a child’s cognitive, emotional, and social development. However, traditional methods of teaching may not always be effective in engaging and motivating young learners. To improve the efficiency of preschool education, it is important to incorporate innovative and engaging teaching methods that cater to different learning styles and abilities. In this article, we will explore some of the ways in which preschool education can be made more efficient and effective.

Play-Based Learning

Play-based learning is an innovative method that uses play as a way of teaching young children. This method involves providing children with toys, games, and activities that are designed to be both fun and educational. Play-based learning encourages children to use their imagination, creativity, and problem-solving skills, and helps to make learning more interesting and relevant.

Research has shown that play-based learning can lead to improvements in children's cognitive, emotional, and social development [1]. By providing children with a more active and hands-on learning experience, play-based learning can help to make learning more engaging and effective.

Nature-Based Learning

Nature-based learning is an innovative method that involves using nature as a way of teaching young children. This method involves taking children outdoors and allowing them to explore and interact with the natural world. Nature-based learning encourages children to use their senses, curiosity, and creativity, and helps to foster a sense of respect and appreciation for the environment.

Research has shown that nature-based learning can lead to improvements in children's cognitive, emotional, and social development [4]. By providing children with a more immersive and experiential learning experience, nature-based learning can help to make learning more engaging and effective.

Technology-Based Learning

Technology-based learning is an innovative method that involves using technology as a way of teaching young children. This method involves providing children with access to educational apps, games, and websites that are designed to be both fun and educational. Technology-based learning encourages children to use their imagination, creativity, and problem-solving skills, and helps to make learning more interactive and engaging.

Research has shown that technology-based learning can lead to improvements in children's cognitive, emotional, and social development [5]. By providing children with a more personalized and interactive learning experience, technology-based learning can help to make learning more engaging and effective.

Mindfulness-Based Learning

Mindfulness-based learning is an innovative method that involves teaching young children to be present in the moment, and to focus on their thoughts and feelings without judgment. Mindfulness-based learning can help to reduce stress and anxiety, and can improve children's ability to concentrate and learn.

Research has shown that mindfulness-based learning can lead to improvements in children's emotional and social development, as well as their academic performance [6]. By promoting a positive and calm learning environment, mindfulness-based learning can help to make learning more effective and efficient.

Multi-Sensory Learning

Multi-sensory learning is an innovative method that involves using multiple senses as a way of teaching young children. This method involves providing children with activities that involve touch, sight, sound, and smell, and that are designed to be both fun and educational. Multi-sensory learning encourages children to use their senses and imagination, and helps to make learning more interesting and relevant.

Research has shown that multi-sensory learning can lead to improvements in children's cognitive, emotional, and social development [2]. By providing children with a more immersive and multi-dimensional learning experience, multi-sensory learning can help to make learning more engaging and effective.

Collaborative Learning

Collaborative learning is an innovative method that involves children working together in groups to solve problems and complete tasks. This method encourages children to use their communication, collaboration, and problem-solving skills, and helps to foster a sense of teamwork and cooperation.

Research has shown that collaborative learning can lead to improvements in children's

cognitive, emotional, and social development [3]. By providing children with opportunities to work together and learn from each other, collaborative learning can help to make learning more engaging and effective.

In conclusion, there are many innovative and incorporating ways to improve the efficiency of preschool education. Play-based learning, nature-based learning, technology-based learning, mindfulness-based learning, multi-sensory learning, and collaborative learning are just a few examples of the many methods that can be used to engage and motivate young learners. By incorporating these methods into preschool education, we can help to create a more efficient and effective learning environment for all children.

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BOLA RIVOJLANISHI SOXALARINING KOMPETENSIYALARI

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Annotatsiya. Maqolada bolaning rivojlanish sohalari kompetensiyalarini shakllantirish masalasi dolzarbligi borasidagi fikrlar keltirilgan. Bolaning rivojlanish sohalari kompetensiyalarining metodologik asoslari ko'rsatib berilgan. Jumladan, maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya sohasiga oid me'yoriy-huquqiy hujjatlarga alohida to'xtalib o'tilgan. Hamda bola tarbiyasiga va uning kelajagiga doir hikmatli so'zlar tahliliy o'rganilgan. Hamda bolaning rivojlanish sohalari kompetensiyalarini shakllantirish masalasi dolzarbligi borasidagi fikrlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: bola, rivojlanish sohalari kompetensiyalari, ijtimoiy-hissiy rivojlanish, nutq, muloqot, o'qish va yozish malakalari, bilish jarayonining rivojlanishi.

Bugungi avlod istiqbolda yangi O'zbekistonning taraqqiyotini ta'minlashi uchun ham jismoniy va ma'naviy sog'lom, intellektual salohiyatli bo'lishi talab etiladi. Bu talab maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya tashkilotlarida voyaga yetayotgan yosh avlodning ta'limi va tarbiyasiga bo'lgan e'tiborni oshirishni taqozo etadi. Shu maqsadda, mamlakatimizda maktabgacha ta'lim tizimini yanada takomillashtirish, moddiy-texnik bazasini mustahkamlash, maktabgacha ta'lim muassasalari tarmog'ini kengaytirish, malakali pedagog kadrlar bilan ta'minlash, bolalarni maktab ta'limiga tayyorlash darajasini tubdan yaxshilash, ta'lim-tarbiya jarayoniga zamonaviy ta'lim dasturlari va texnologiyalarni tadbiiq etish, bolalarni har tomonlama intellektual, ahloqiy, estetik va jismoniy rivojlantirish uchun shart-sharoitlar yaratish bo'yicha muhim ishlar amalga oshirildi. 2020-yil 22-dekabrda O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining "Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiyaning davlat standartini tasdiqlashtirish to'g'risida"gi VMQ 802-sonli Qarori[1] qabul qilindi. Ushbu qarorga binoan bolaning rivojlanish sohalari kompetensiyalari belgilab berildi.